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Impact of climate change on solar and wind energy: *Insights from a convection permitting climate model ensemble*

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Overview

- I. **Solar energy:** Future change in Photovoltaic generation potential over Italy
- II. **Wind energy:** Future change in 50-year wind speeds and its impact on turbine class requirements

Ensemble of Convection Permitting Models (CPMs) - CORDEX Flagship Pilot Study on Convective phenomena (CORDEX-FPS Conv)

- Horizontal resolution :2.2 to 3 km (remapped to 3km grid)
- Temporal resolution: 1 hr
- **Nested in a 12km European domain in turn driven by a GCM**
- CPMs belong to 5 model families: **COSMO, AROME, WRF and RegCM**
- Better represent orography, land-sea interactions, extreme precipitation events and surface wind speeds

Evaluation

- ERA-Interim driven
- 2000 - 2009

Historical

- GCM driven
- 1996-2005

RCP-8.5

- GCM driven
- 2090-2099

Solar energy : Assessment of Photovoltaic potential over Italy using a convection permitting climate model ensemble

Photovoltaic (PV) potential model

Energy production relative to nominal production capacity

Shortwave radiation

(adapted from Jerez et al., 2015)

$$PV\ potential(t) = P_R(t) \frac{RSDS(t)}{RSDS_{STC}}$$

Cell efficiency:
depends PV cell temperature

$$P_R(t) = 1 - \gamma [T_{cell}(t) - T_{STC}]$$

depends on surface temperature (**TAS**)
wind speed (**VWS**) and **RSDS**

Parameter	Value
$RSDS_{STC}$	1000 W/m ²
T_{STC}	25°C
γ	0.005 / °C

Future changes in climate variables influencing PV potential

$$PVpotential(t) = P_R(t) \frac{RSDS(t)}{RSDS_{STC}}$$

Surface downwelling shortwave radiation (**RSDS**)

- Statistically significant increase in shortwave radiation during summer over most of Italy (~2.2%)
- Despite shared GCM driving, **CNRM** and **BTU** project the highest and lowest RSDS changes, respectively

Future change in climate variables influencing PV potential

$$PVpotential(t) = P_R(t) \frac{RSDS(t)}{RSDS_{STC}}$$

Surface air temperature (TAS)

- Statistically significant rise in temperatures by + 5°C over the entire country
- **ICTP** and **AUTH-BCCR** are the most climate sensitive

Future changes in PV potential (PVpot)

- Ensemble median suggests a **slight decline (~2%)** in **central-southern** part of Italy and **sight increase/no-change** in the **North**
- **Rise in temperatures offset the rise in radiation.**
- PV panels with higher nominal operating temperatures could generate more, leveraging higher RSDS.

Summary – Future change in PV potential over Italy

- CPM ensemble indicates that **PV production in Italy will not be significantly threatened by climate change** in future, supporting the ongoing expansion of PV installed capacity.
- **Rapid rise in temperature** drive the change in PV potential and in future, **lower temperature sensitivity or panel cooling** could be means to leverage projected increase in radiation.
- Considerable **inter-model spread** among CPMs driven by same GCM, suggest the influence of **aerosol forcings, radiation and cloud parameterizations** are dominant for RSDS projection

Wind energy :

Future change in 50-year wind speeds and its impact on turbine class requirements

Extreme winds and design class requirements for wind turbines

- **Extreme wind speeds** can lead to large wind turbine loads, and threaten its structural integrity
- **International Electro-technical Commission (IEC)** standards mandate the choice of wind turbine class based on **U50**: the **50-year return period wind speed (10-minute average)**.
- **100m wind speeds** from CPM simulations are used to project end of century changes in U50 and turbine class requirements.

Wind turbine class	III	II	I	T	S
U50 (m/s)	37.5	42.5	50	57	Values specified by designer

Validation: Wind power spectrum

- All **CPMs** well represent wind power spectra at the mast location, until close to its temporal resolution
- **Spectral correction** method to capture missing sub-hourly variability in mesoscale models.
 - Modelled spectra in the high frequency range (10 min – 1 day) are replaced with a theoretical $f^{-5/3}$ **slope** commonly observed for mesoscale winds.
- Corrected annual maxima (**10 minute effective resolution**) is fit to **Gumbel distribution** to estimate 50 year wind speeds (**U50**)

Validation: U50 estimates

- Most models show a bias in U50 of +/- 2.5 m/s
- **Ensemble median U50 value of 28.1m/s (+1.1 m/s overestimation)**
- Large overestimations in AUTH, ICTP and ETH

U50 in CPMs vs GASP (Global atlas for siting parameters)

- Higher U50 magnitude and spatial variability in CPMs close to mountains
- Slight underestimation over the Mediterranean.
- High overestimation in AUTH-WRF381BG, as observed at the measurement location

Turbine class in CPMs vs GASP

- Larger proportion of land with turbine class II or higher in CPMs
- **Higher turbine class in CPM along complex orography, marked with high uncertainty in GASP**
- **Lower class requirement over parts of Mediterranean in CPMs**

Future changes in U50

- Large spatial variability in U50 changes
- All models, except HCLIMcom depict an overall increase over the domain
- Largest increase in ETH and AUTH

Future changes in Turbine class

End-Century Change

- Ensemble median changes: **increase** in turbine class over **+6%** area and **decrease over 1%** area
- Spatially consistent **increases** concentrated along the **Ligurian and Adriatic coasts**
- KNMI shows the least change in turbine class

Uncertainties in future projections

End Century - Model agreement on change in class

- **Low inter-model agreement over complex orography and parts of the Mediterranean**
- Sources of uncertainty:
 - Forcing GCM
 - Choice of RCM
 - Model configuration and parametrizations
 - Limited time period for estimation of U50

Summary – Future change in U50 and turbine class requirements

- CPM ensemble **well represent** observed **wind spectra** at the measurement location, close to its temporal resolution
- CPMs display **realistic spatial variability in U50 values and turbine class**
- Ensemble median U50 changes suggest a **higher turbine class in ~5% of area** and **lower turbine class in ~1% of area** covered by the CPM domain
- Uncertainties and role of physical mechanisms responsible for the annual maxima wind speeds to be investigated further

Thanks for your attention!

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Annexure

Evaluation of radiation and cloud cover from CPMs

RSDS bias relative to SARAH-3

Cloud cover bias relative to CLARA-A3

IEC standards

Table 1 – Basic parameters for wind turbine classes

Wind turbine class		I	II	III	S
V_{ave}	(m/s)	10	8,5	7,5	Values specified by the designer
V_{ref}	(m/s)	50	42,5	37,5	
	Tropical (m/s) $V_{ref,T}$	57	57	57	
A+	I_{ref} (-)	0,18			
A	I_{ref} (-)	0,16			
B	I_{ref} (-)	0,14			
C	I_{ref} (-)	0,12			

The parameter values apply at hub height and

V_{ave} is the annual average wind speed;

V_{ref} is the reference wind speed average over 10 min;

$V_{ref,T}$ is the reference wind speed average over 10 min applicable for areas subject to tropical cyclones;

A+ designates the category for very high turbulence characteristics;

A designates the category for higher turbulence characteristics;

B designates the category for medium turbulence characteristics;

C designates the category for lower turbulence characteristics; and

I_{ref} is a reference value of the turbulence intensity (see 6.3.2.3).

Wind power spectra in CPM vs Observation

- KNMI and HCLIMcom has 3 hourly resolution while all other CPMs have hourly resolution
- All CPMs well represent wind power spectra at the mast location, until close to the Nyquist frequency corresponding to its temporal resolution (8 day^{-1} for hourly resolution and 2 day^{-1} for 3-hourly resolution)
- AROME and WRF models show a more pronounced diurnal peak compared to observation
- IDL-WRF381BH has considerably higher power spectral density relative to observations

Spectral Correction of wind speeds

- Statistical method to account for missing variability in wind speed at high frequency range (sub-hourly) observed in mesoscale models (*Larsén et al., 2012*)
- Replaces modelled spectra in the (10min – 1 day) frequency range with theoretical slope $f^{-5/3}$ observed at mesoscales
- Derives correction factor for a location proportional to the ratio of moments (m_0 and m_2) of original and corrected spectra

$$m_0 = \int S(f) df \text{ and } m_2 = \int f^2 S(f) df$$

$$\text{Peak factor, } k_p = \sqrt{2 \ln \left(\frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{m_2}{m_0}} T_0 \right)}$$

$$\text{Smoothing effect, } SE_{k_p} = 1 - k_{p,1h} / k_{p,corr}$$

$$\text{Corrected maxima, } \bar{U}_{max,corr,ts} = \bar{U}_{max,corr,ts} / (1 - SE_{U_{max}})$$

Uncertainty in U50 estimates from GASP

Future change in 99 percentile wind speeds

- Most CPMs project an increase in 99th percentile of wind speeds except ICTP, HCLIMcom and AUTH
- Consistent changes for models driven with same GCM
- Over sea, more consistent increases over the Adriatic and north of Corsica

Change in 99th percentile

Change in U50

Ensemble of CPMs used:

	Institute	CPM (original resolution)	RCM (original resolution)	GCM
1	AUTH-BCCR	WRF-381DA (3 km)	(15 km)	NorESM1-ME
2	HCLIM	HCLIM38-AROME (3 km)	HCLIM38-ALADIN (12 km)	EC-Earth
3	KNMI	HCLIM38hi-AROME (2.5 km)	RACMO23 (12 km)	
4	FZJ-IDL	WRF-381CA (3km)	15km	
5		WRF-381DA (3km)	15km	
6	BTU	CCLM5-0-9 (3 km)	(12 km)	
7	CNRM	CNRM-AROME41t1 (2.5 km)	CNRM-ALADIN63 (12.5 km)	
8	KIT	CCLM5-0-14 (2.5 km)	(25 km)	MPI-ESM-LR
9	JLU	CCLM5-0-10 (3 km)	No nest	

	Acronym	CPM (original resolution)	RCM (original resolution)	GCM
10	ETH	COSMO-crCLIM (2.2 km)	(12 km)	MPI
11	CMCC	CCLM5-0-9 (3 km)	CCLM4 (12 km)	CMCC
12	IPSL-WEGC	WRF-381DA (3 km)	15 km	IPSL-CM5A-MR
13	IPSL	WRF-381CA (3 km)	15 km	
14	ICTP	RegCM4 (3 km)	RegCM4 (12 km)	HadGEM